

11-16 AUGUST 2019
22nd International Conference
on Composite Materials

Fatigue life prognosis for composite laminates using lamb wave velocity

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Motivation

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Composite materials have been used extensively

Composites **degrade** under cyclic loadings

Material used in the Boeing 787

This is a problem!!!

Motivation

- General concept

Difficult to measure

Easier to measure

Motivation

Life prediction is made in stage II

- I. A fast decrease in stiffness caused by matrix cracks in off-axis plies
- II. Gradual and slow material degradation
- III. Unsteady and fast loss of stiffness before final collapse

$$c_p^{f_0, S_0} = \sqrt{\frac{E_x}{(1 - \nu_{xy}\nu_{yx})\rho}}$$

Phase velocity is the square root of stiffness

Life prediction based on residual wave velocity relies heavily on accurate extraction of velocity

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Damage model

- Stiffness degradation

Stage I: A fast decrease in stiffness caused by matrix cracks in off-axis plies

Stage II: Gradual and slow material degradation

Stage III: Unsteady and fast loss of stiffness before final collapse

Fiber damages: Fibers are generally considered to be immune to fatigue damages

Matrix cracks: Form in the off-axis plies, along the fiber direction, major contribution to the stiffness degradation

Delamination: Usually triggered by matrix cracks or fiber damages, minor contribution to the stiffness degradation

Damage model

- Fiber damage

Notable decrease after 1st load cycle

Fiber damage factor :

Stiffness $D_f = 1 - \frac{E_{x1}}{E_0}$

Velocity: $D_f = 1 - \frac{c_{x1}^2}{c_0^2}$

- Delamination

Stiffness loss caused by delamination is simplified by a simple linear relation:

$$D_{dela} = D_d * N$$

Damage model

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- Matrix cracks

Unifying shear lag expression:

$$E_x = \frac{E_0}{1 + a\rho_c R(\bar{l}_c)}$$

Note it is very difficult to obtain crack density information in real application

$$E_x = E_0[1 - D_c(1 - e^{-c\rho_c})]$$

D_c is a characteristic damage factor

$$D_c = 1 - \frac{E_l \cdot h_l}{E \cdot h}$$

Comparison between shear-lag model, proposed approximation and linear approximation

Damage model

- Matrix cracks

Shear-lag model approximation

$$E_x(\rho_c) = E_{x1}(1 - D_{mc})$$

$$E_x(2\rho_c) = E_{x1} \left(\frac{D_c - 2D_c D_{mc} + D_{mc}^2}{D_c} \right)$$

$$\rho_c = \frac{\log(D_c) - \log(D_c - D_{mc})}{c}$$

Matrix cracks is the core of three damage mechanisms!!!

Strain energy release rate for formation of new matrix cracks

$$G = \frac{B\sigma_x^2}{2\rho_c} \left(-\frac{1}{E_x(\rho_c)} + \frac{1}{E_x(2\rho_c)} \right)$$

$$\Delta G = \frac{cB\sigma_x^2(1 - R^2)D_{mc}(D_c - D_{mc})}{\log\left(\frac{D_c}{D_c - D_{mc}}\right)(D_c - 2D_c D_{mc} + D_{mc}^2)(1 - D_{mc})}$$

Paris law

$$\frac{d\rho}{dN} = c(\Delta G)^m$$

$$\frac{dD_{mc}}{dN} = c(\Delta G)^m$$

Model parameter

- Bayesian inference

Bayes' theorem: $q(\boldsymbol{\theta}|d) \propto p(\boldsymbol{\theta})p(d|\boldsymbol{\theta})$

Transform in to a statistical model: $x' = D(N, \boldsymbol{\theta}) + \epsilon_1 + \epsilon_2$

Posterior distribution: $q(\boldsymbol{\theta}|d) \propto p(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_\delta^2}} \exp\left[-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{(x' - D(N, \boldsymbol{\theta}))^2}{\sigma_\delta^2}\right)\right]$

Markov chain: $r = \min\left(1, \frac{g(\theta^*)h(\theta^{(t-1)}|\theta^*)}{g(\theta)h(\theta^*|\theta^{(t-1)})}\right)$

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Experiments

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- Specimen

Geometry:

Material properties:

Lamina properties
$E_1 = 43.16\text{GPa}$
$E_2 = 10.81\text{GPa}$
$\mu_{12} = 0.31$
$G_{12} = 4.85\text{GPa}$
Nominal ply thickness=0.106mm

- Experimental setup

Stiffness

- Experimental results

No obvious fiber damage

Fiber damage

Velocity

- Experimental results

Severity	Fatigue life
55%	1437
50%	3545
45%	5511

Failure threshold

Fatigue life

- Bayesian inference without prior

55%

50%

45%

Fatigue life

- Bayesian inference with prior

55%

50%

45%

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Conclusion

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Works have been done

- *A stiffness/velocity degradation model is proposed*
- *Bayesian inference is used to obtain the posterior distribution of model parameters*
- *Lamb wave velocity is measured with laser ultrasonic method*
- *Fatigue life prediction is realized in a statistical framework*

Works to be done

- *Accuracy*
- *Efficiency*
- *Generality*

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